

DISPLACEMENT POTENTIAL SOLUTION TO ELASTIC FIELD IN A STIFFENED CANTILEVER OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

The mixed boundary value elasticity problem of a stiffened cantilever of laminated composite is formulated in terms of a single displacement potential function. This reduces the problem to the solution of a single fourth order partial differential equation. Analytical solution is presented for a glass/epoxy cantilever under a tip load.

Keywords: Mixed boundary condition, Analytical solution, Displacement potential approach, Elastic field, Cantilever, Laminated composite

INTRODUCTION

It is now well known that composite materials are superior to conventional monolithic materials in many respects. In particular, these materials possess superior mechanical properties, such as specific strength and stiffness, superior physical property, such as specific density, and superior thermal property, such as minimized coefficient of thermal expansion. As a result, these materials are being widely used in modern structural elements to exhibit better characteristics. However, the characteristics of a structural element are dependent on both the geometry of the element and boundary conditions experienced by the element. Therefore, for a particular application, a structural element should be properly analyzed in order to understand, quantify, and improve the characteristics satisfying all the necessary boundary conditions to the desired level of accuracy. Elastic behavior is one of the important issues that should be paid attention to understand the stress and displacement fields. This necessitates a suitable analysis method that is capable of dealing with any boundary conditions.

Airy stress function approach can be used to obtain analytical solution only for some idealized two dimensional problems when boundary conditions are prescribed in terms of stresses only. This approach appears to be inadequate for the problems when the boundary conditions are prescribed in terms of displacement or strain. Displacement boundary conditions can be treated if the problems are formulated in terms of displacement parameters [1]. However, this involves two major difficulties. Firstly, formulations of two dimensional elasticity problems in terms of displacement parameters yields two simultaneous second order partial differential equations which are

quite difficult to solve analytically. Secondly, the mixed boundary conditions cannot be dealt with by this approach.

Displacement potential approach is a relatively new approach which has gained importance in the field of two dimensional elasticity problems because of its outstanding advantage that it can deal with any modes of boundary conditions, whether prescribed in terms of either stress or displacement or any combination of these, i.e. mixed boundary conditions. In this approach, both the displacement parameters are defined in terms of a single function, called displacement potential function, such that one of the equilibrium equations is satisfied automatically. Thus, the problem is reduced to the solution of a single fourth order partial differential equation. Originally, this approach was introduced for isotropic materials [2] which was later extended for orthotropic laminas [3]. To deal with more practical problems, the approach was further extended for laminated composites [4] as most of the structural elements consist of laminates instead of a single lamina. In an attempt to verify and examine the extent of capability of the approach, it is applied, in this study, to a deep and thin cantilever beam of cross-ply and angle-ply laminated composites with mixed boundary conditions to obtain exact solution and carry out the analysis of elastic field due to a tip load. The effects of stacking sequence of the cross-ply laminate and angle of the angle-ply laminate on the elastic field are investigated in details.

DISPLACEMENT POTENTIAL FORMULATION

For a symmetric laminate subjected to an in-plane loading, the bending-extension coupling stiffness matrix vanishes [5] and the mid-plane strains become equal to the global strains. Furthermore, for a cross-ply laminate and an angle-ply laminate with even number of plies, the shear-extension coupling terms of the extensional stiffness matrix are banished. For such laminates, the average stress-strain relations under plane stress in global coordinate system can be formulated as [5, 6]

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{h} \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ_x and σ_y are the components of normal stress in the x - and y -directions, respectively, τ_{xy} is the shear stress component, ε_x and ε_y are the normal strain components in the x - and y -directions, respectively, γ_{xy} is the shear strain component, and the elements of stiffness matrix $[A]$ are given by

$$A_{11} = \sum_{k=1}^n [Q_{11}c^4 + Q_{22}s^4 + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})s^2c^2]_k (h_k - h_{k-1}) \quad (2a)$$

$$A_{12} = \sum_{k=1}^n [(Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66})s^2c^2 + Q_{12}(c^4 + s^4)]_k (h_k - h_{k-1}) \quad (2b)$$

$$A_{22} = \sum_{k=1}^n [Q_{11}s^4 + Q_{22}c^4 + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})s^2c^2]_k (h_k - h_{k-1}) \quad (2c)$$

$$A_{66} = \sum_{k=1}^n [(Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})s^2c^2 + Q_{66}(s^4 + c^4)]_k (h_k - h_{k-1}) \quad (2d)$$

Here, $Q_{11} = E_1(1 - \nu_{21}\nu_{12})^{-1}$, $Q_{12} = \nu_{12}E_2(1 - \nu_{21}\nu_{12})^{-1}$, $Q_{22} = E_2(1 - \nu_{21}\nu_{12})^{-1}$, $Q_{66} = G_{12}$, $c = \cos \theta$, $s = \sin \theta$, $h_k - h_{k-1}$ is the thickness of the k -th ply of the laminate, h is the total thickness of the laminate, θ is the angle between the x -axis and the fiber direction of a lamina in the laminate, E_1 and E_2 are the Young's modulus in the longitudinal and the transverse directions, respectively, ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the major and minor Poisson's ratios, respectively, and G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus of a lamina in the laminate.

Substitution of Eq. (1) and making use of strain-displacement relations into two dimensional equilibrium equations without body forces yields

$$A_{11} \frac{\partial^2 u_x}{\partial x^2} + (A_{12} + A_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 u_y}{\partial x \partial y} + A_{66} \frac{\partial^2 u_x}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$A_{22} \frac{\partial^2 u_y}{\partial y^2} + (A_{12} + A_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 u_x}{\partial x \partial y} + A_{66} \frac{\partial^2 u_y}{\partial x^2} = 0 \quad (3b)$$

Although the above two equations are theoretically sufficient to solve for two displacement parameters u_x and u_y , it is in fact very difficult to solve two second order partial differential simultaneous equations analytically. One way to get rid of this problem is to reduce the number of equation which is outlined in the sequel.

Displacement Potential Function

If the two unknown displacement parameters u_x and u_y can be expressed in terms of the same function $\psi(x, y)$, the number of unknowns will be reduced to one. However, it implies that there will be only one equation for the determination of one unknown function. Therefore, the two displacement parameters u_x and u_y are defined in terms of the single function $\psi(x, y)$ in such a way that one of the equilibrium equations in Eq. (3) is satisfied automatically. The function $\psi(x, y)$ is called displacement potential function and is defined as

$$u_x = \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (4a)$$

$$u_y = -\frac{A_{11}}{A_{12} + A_{66}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{A_{66}}{A_{12} + A_{66}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \quad (4b)$$

Fig. 1 A cantilever beam of laminated composite under parabolic shear load at the tip.

The above definition of $\psi(x, y)$ satisfies the first equilibrium equation in Eq. (3) and the second equilibrium equation is reduced to

$$\frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial x^4} + \left[\frac{A_{22}}{A_{66}} - \frac{A_{12}^2}{A_{11}A_{66}} - \frac{2A_{12}}{A_{11}} \right] \frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{A_{22}}{A_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial y^4} = 0 \quad (5)$$

By making use of Eqs. (1), (4), and strain-displacement relations, the components of stress can be expressed in terms of the same displacement potential function $\psi(x, y)$ as

$$\sigma_x = \frac{A_{66}}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})} \left[A_{11} \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^2 \partial y} - A_{12} \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial y^3} \right] \quad (6a)$$

$$\sigma_y = \frac{1}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})} \left[(A_{12}^2 + A_{12}A_{66} - A_{11}A_{22}) \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^2 \partial y} - A_{22}A_{66} \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial y^3} \right] \quad (6b)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = \frac{A_{66}}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})} \left[A_{12} \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x \partial y^2} - A_{11} \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3} \right] \quad (6c)$$

Equation (5) is a fourth order partial differential equation for a single unknown function $\psi(x, y)$. Once this equation is solved for $\psi(x, y)$, the components of displacement and stress can readily be determined from Eqs. (4) and (6), respectively.

CANTILEVER BEAM

Analytical Model

The formulations developed in the preceding sections can be used to obtain the solution of elastic field in a cantilever beam of laminated composite. Figure 1 shows a thin deep cantilever of length b and height a . A Cartesian coordinate system x - y is considered with the origin located at the left lower corner of the beam and the x - and y -axes aligned with the longitudinal and lateral edges of the beam, respectively. The left lateral edge is

rigidly fixed and the two longitudinal edges parallel to the x -axis are stiffened. Application of stiffeners to structural elements is a common practice to improve the stiffness which, in turn, reduces the degree of deformation. The stiffeners are mathematically modelled by imposing zero deformation along their length. The right lateral edge is subjected to a parabolic shear load $\sigma_{xy}^0 = 4P(y^2 - ay)/a^2$, where P is the maximum value of the stress at the center of the edge. It is noted that a load at the tip of a cantilever can be simulated as a parabolic shear load [7]. As the thickness of the cantilever is small in comparison with other dimensions, the analysis can be carried out under plane stress condition. The relevant boundary conditions are:

- (1) $u_x(x, 0) = u_x(x, a) = 0; 0 \leq x \leq b$ (upper and lower stiffened edges)
- (2) $\sigma_y(x, 0) = \sigma_y(x, a) = 0; 0 \leq x \leq b$ (upper and lower stiffened edges)
- (3) $u_x(0, y) = u_y(0, y) = 0; 0 \leq y \leq a$ (left fixed edge)
- (4) $\sigma_x(b, y) = 0, \sigma_{xy}(b, y) = \sigma_{xy}^0 = 4P(y^2 - ay)/a^2; 0 \leq y \leq a$ (right lateral edge).

Solution of the Problem

Although a lot of expressions for $\psi(x, y)$ may satisfy Eq. (5), its selection must consider the fact that all the boundary conditions should be satisfied exactly in order to obtain the exact solution of the problem. Keeping this in mind, the displacement potential function $\psi(x, y)$ is chosen in the form of a series as

$$\psi = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} X_m \cos \alpha y + Mx^3 \quad (7)$$

where X_m is the function of x only, $\alpha = m\pi/a$, and M is an arbitrary constant. Combination of Eqs. (5) and (7) yields a fourth order ordinary differential equation with constant coefficients as

$$X_m'''' - BX_m''\alpha^2 + CX_m\alpha^4 = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $B = \frac{A_{22}}{A_{66}} - \frac{A_{12}^2}{A_{11}A_{66}} - \frac{2A_{12}}{A_{11}}$ and $C = \frac{A_{22}}{A_{11}}$. The solution of Eq. (8) is obtained as

$$X_m = A_m e^{n_1 x} + B_m e^{n_2 x} + C_m e^{n_3 x} + D_m e^{n_4 x} \quad (9)$$

where

$$n_1, n_2 = \alpha \sqrt{(B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4C}) / 2} \quad (10a)$$

$$n_3, n_4 = -\alpha \sqrt{(B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4C}) / 2} \quad (10b)$$

and $A_m, B_m, C_m,$ and D_m are arbitrary constants. Now, by making use of Eqs. (7) and (9) into Eqs. (4) and (6), the components of displacement and stress can be expressed as

$$u_x(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[- (n_1 A_m e^{n_1 x} + n_2 B_m e^{n_2 x} + n_3 C_m e^{n_3 x} + n_4 D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha \sin \alpha y \right] \quad (11a)$$

$$u_y(x, y) = \frac{1}{A_{12} + A_{66}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[\begin{array}{l} \left\{ A_{66} (A_m e^{n_1 x} + B_m e^{n_2 x} + C_m e^{n_3 x} + D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha^2 \right. \\ \left. - A_{11} (n_1^2 A_m e^{n_1 x} + n_2^2 B_m e^{n_2 x} + n_3^2 C_m e^{n_3 x} + n_4^2 D_m e^{n_4 x}) \right\} \cos \alpha y \\ - 6Mx A_{11} \end{array} \right] \quad (11b)$$

$$\sigma_x(x, y) = -\frac{A_{66}}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[\begin{array}{l} A_{12} (A_m e^{n_1 x} + B_m e^{n_2 x} + C_m e^{n_3 x} + D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha^3 + \\ A_{11} (n_1^2 A_m e^{n_1 x} + n_2^2 B_m e^{n_2 x} + n_3^2 C_m e^{n_3 x} + n_4^2 D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha \end{array} \right] \sin \alpha y \quad (12a)$$

$$\sigma_y(x, y) = -\frac{1}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[\begin{array}{l} A_{22} A_{66} (A_m e^{n_1 x} + B_m e^{n_2 x} + C_m e^{n_3 x} + D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha^3 + \\ (A_{12}^2 + A_{12} A_{66} - A_{11} A_{22}) \\ (n_1^2 A_m e^{n_1 x} + n_2^2 B_m e^{n_2 x} + n_3^2 C_m e^{n_3 x} + n_4^2 D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha \end{array} \right] \sin \alpha y \quad (12b)$$

$$\sigma_{xy}(x, y) = -\frac{A_{66}}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[\begin{array}{l} A_{12} (n_1 A_m e^{n_1 x} + n_2 B_m e^{n_2 x} + n_3 C_m e^{n_3 x} + n_4 D_m e^{n_4 x}) \alpha^2 + \\ A_{11} (n_1^3 A_m e^{n_1 x} + n_2^3 B_m e^{n_2 x} + n_3^3 C_m e^{n_3 x} + n_4^3 D_m e^{n_4 x}) \end{array} \right] \cos \alpha y \quad (12c)$$

$$-\frac{6MA_1 A_{66}}{h(A_{12} + A_{66})}$$

With the above expressions of displacement and stress, it is found that the boundary conditions (1) and (2) are satisfied automatically. Thus, the boundary conditions (3) and (4) are remaining to be satisfied. Before application of the boundary conditions (3) and (4), the parabolic applied load at the edge $x = b$ is expressed in terms of Fourier series as

$$\sigma_{xy}^0(b, y) = E_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} E_m \cos \alpha y \quad (13)$$

where $E_0 = -2P/3$ and $E_m = 8P[1 + \cos(m\pi)]/m^2\pi^2$. Now, applying the boundary conditions (3) and (4) into Eqs. (11), (12a), and (12c), one obtains the constant M as

$$M = hP(A_{12} + A_{66})/9A_{11}A_{66} \quad (14)$$

Table 1 Mechanical Properties of a glass/epoxy unidirectional lamina

E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	G_{12} (MPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{21}
38.60×10^3	8.27×10^3	4.14×10^3	0.26	0.06

and the following four simultaneous equations for the determination of the constants A_m , B_m , C_m , and D_m .

$$n_1 A_m + n_2 B_m + n_3 C_m + n_4 D_m = 0 \quad ; \quad 0 < y < a \quad (15a)$$

$$(A_{11} n_1^2 - A_{66} \alpha^2) A_m + (A_{11} n_2^2 - A_{66} \alpha^2) B_m + (A_{11} n_3^2 - A_{66} \alpha^2) C_m + (A_{11} n_4^2 - A_{66} \alpha^2) D_m = 0 \quad (15b)$$

$$(A_{11} n_1^2 \alpha + A_{12} \alpha^3) A_m e^{n_1 b} + (A_{11} n_2^2 \alpha + A_{12} \alpha^3) B_m e^{n_2 b} + (A_{11} n_3^2 \alpha + A_{12} \alpha^3) C_m e^{n_3 b} + (A_{11} n_4^2 \alpha + A_{12} \alpha^3) D_m e^{n_4 b} = 0 \quad (15c)$$

$$(A_{11} n_1^3 + A_{12} n_1 \alpha^2) A_m e^{n_1 b} + (A_{11} n_2^3 + A_{12} n_2 \alpha^2) B_m e^{n_2 b} + (A_{11} n_3^3 + A_{12} n_3 \alpha^2) C_m e^{n_3 b} + (A_{11} n_4^3 + A_{12} n_4 \alpha^2) D_m e^{n_4 b} = -E_m h (A_{12} + A_{66}) / A_{66} \quad (15d)$$

The constants A_m , B_m , C_m , and D_m obtained from the above equations are substituted into Eqs. (11) and (12) to obtain the explicit expressions of displacement and stress which are valid to the entire region of the cantilever.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To obtain some numerical results, a cantilever of glass/epoxy laminated composite is considered. The properties of a unidirectional glass/epoxy composite lamina are shown in Table 1. All the results presented in this section correspond to the aspect ratio of the beam $b/a = 3.0$. The value of P is taken as 1000 MPa and the thickness of each ply is taken as 1.0 mm. The convergence of the results is ensured by varying the number of terms m in the series solution. It is found that the results converge very well for $m = 100$.

Figure 2 shows the normalized longitudinal displacement u_x/b at different sections of the cantilever as a function of normalized position y/a . As seen, the displacement is zero at the section $x/b = 0$ and at the top ($y/a = 1.0$) and bottom ($y/a = 0$) edges of the cantilever. This satisfies the physical boundary conditions of the problem. The maximum displacement occurs at the right lateral edge ($x/b = 1.0$) and it gradually decreases towards the fixed support ($x/b = 0$). Shown in Fig. 3 is the normalized lateral displacement (u_y/a) at different sections of the cantilever. The lateral displacement is exactly zero at the fixed support ($x/b = 0$) which satisfies the boundary conditions of the problem. The magnitude of this displacement is also the maximum at the right lateral edge and gradually diminishes towards the fixed support. Further, the variation of the displacement with y/a is almost zero at all the sections except the right lateral edge. The distribution of normalized longitudinal stress component (σ_x/P) as a function of normalized position (y/a) is illustrated in Fig. 4. At the right lateral edge ($x/b = 1.0$), the stress is zero that satisfies the boundary condition of the problem. Further, the longitudinal stress is zero at the fixed support and at the top and bottom stiffened edges of the cantilever. The magnitude of the stress is maximum near the right lateral edge of

Fig. 2 Longitudinal displacement.

Fig. 3 Lateral displacement.

the cantilever and it gradually decrease towards the fixed support. The normalized lateral stress component (σ_y/P) is displayed in Fig. 5. The distribution of this stress component is similar to that of the longitudinal stress component except that this stress is the maximum at the right lateral edge. Figure 6 depicts the distribution of normalized shear stress component (σ_{xy}/P). At the right lateral edge ($x/b = 1.0$), the distribution of the shear stress exactly matches with the applied load. Generally speaking, the magnitude of the shear stress decreases towards the fixed support of the cantilever.

To investigate the effect of stacking sequence of a cross-ply laminate consisting of three plies on the elastic field, four different stacking sequences, $[0/0/0]$, $[0/90/0]$, $[90/0/90]$, and $[90/90/90]$, are considered. Some representative results at the section $x/b = 0.75$ are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. The results show that the maximum lateral displacement and longitudinal stress occur when all the plies have 0° orientation. Their magnitudes are found to decrease as the number of 90° plies increases. Further, the range of variation of the displacement and stress decreases as the number of 90° plies increases.

The present displacement potential formulations can also be applied to the case of an angle-ply laminate. The formulations are demonstrated for a cantilever of angle-ply

Fig. 4 Longitudinal stress.

Fig. 5 Lateral stress.

Fig. 6 Shear stress.

Fig. 7 Effect of stacking sequence on lateral displacement.

laminates consisting of four plies. The effect of the angles of the plies on the elastic field is illustrated in Figs. 9 and 10 which show some representative results of the longitudinal displacement and lateral stress at three points of the section $x/b = 0.75$. The longitudinal displacement is zero at $y/a = 0.5$ which remains unaffected by the ply angle. However, the magnitude of the displacement at the points other than $y/a = 0.5$ varies significantly with the ply angle. As seen from Fig. 9, the displacements at the points $y/a = 0.25$ and 0.75 are maximum when the ply angle is zero. With the increase of the ply angle, the magnitude of the displacements decreases. The lateral stress at the point $y/a = 0.5$ is zero and remains unaffected by the ply angle as seen from Fig. 10. At $y/a = 0.25$ and 0.75 , the magnitude of the lateral stress increases with the increase of the ply angle and attains the maximum value at the ply angle of around 37° . With further increase of the ply angle, the magnitude of the stress starts decreasing until the ply angle of around 65° . The stress does not vary if the ply angle further increases from 65° .

CONCLUSIONS

The displacement potential approach is used to obtain the analytical solution of the elastic field in a stiffened cantilever beam of laminated composite. The two-dimensional mixed boundary value problem is formulated in terms of a single displacement potential function that reduces the problem to the solution of a single fourth-order differential equation. The formulation is demonstrated for a glass/epoxy cantilever under parabolic shear load. Both the qualitative and quantitative results ensure the capability of the approach to obtain analytical results of the elastic field satisfying all the boundary conditions exactly.

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Fig. 8 Effect of stacking sequence on longitudinal stress.

Fig. 9 Effect of ply-angle on longitudinal displacement.

Fig. 10 Effect of ply-angle on lateral stress.

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